

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

Deliverable: D7.4 Infrastructures integration report (interim)

28/02/2021

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448.

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Document Id	D7.4		
Document Title	Infrastructures integration report (interim)		
Due Date	28-Feb-2021	Delivery Date	16-Mar-2021
Lead Beneficiary	SZTAKI		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA, INAF, SZTAKI, CITE, MEEO, ALTEC, GARR, UOP		
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Workpackages	WP7-Delivery		
Version	V1.0	Stage	Draft
Version details	Revision: 15 . Last save: 2021-03-16 , 09:51 Pages: 30 . Characters: 4.799		
Distribution	Public	Type	Report
Keywords	EOSC, Security, Underwater Research, Planetary Science, Astrophysics, Atmospheric Research, Software delivery, Infrastructure, Integration, Deployment		

Document Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1.0	08/03/2021	Document version submitted to EC	József Kovács	

Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Document Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Tables of Figures & Tables	7
Abstract	8
1. Resources of the NEANIAS infrastructure	9
1.1. Compute resources	9
1.1.1. GARR Cloud Platform.....	9
1.1.2. GARR Container Platform	9
1.1.3. NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster	10
1.1.4. NKUA cluster.....	10
1.1.5. ATHENA IT infrastructure	10
1.1.6. CITE infrastructure.....	11
1.1.7. MEE0 Data Center.....	12
1.1.8. HPC4AI infrastructure.....	12
1.1.9. ELKH Cloud.....	12
1.2. Storage resources and repositories	13
1.2.1. GARR Cloud Storage	13
1.2.2. NEANIAS GitLab repository.....	14
1.2.3. Readthedocs repository.....	14
1.2.4. NEANIAS Space repositories at IA2.....	15
1.2.5. MEE0 storage and repositories.....	15
1.3. Networking.....	16
1.3.1. Architecture, capabilities, functionalities of the GARR network	16
1.4. Security entities and mechanisms.....	17
1.4.1. PKI, Certificates.....	17
1.4.2. GARR Cloud Authentication Mechanisms.....	17
1.4.3. Gitlab Token.....	18
1.4.4. AAI.....	18
1.4.5. Reverse proxy.....	20
2. Integration policies in the NEANIAS infrastructure	21
2.1. Documentation Rendering	21
2.2. Code Release	21
2.3. Integration	21
2.3.1. Authentication	21
2.3.2. Logging	22

Infrastructures integration report (interim)

2.3.3.	<i>Accounting</i>	23
2.3.4.	<i>Data Sharing Service</i>	24
2.3.5.	<i>Service Catalogue</i>	24
2.4.	Packaging.....	25
2.5.	Testing	25
2.6.	Deployment.....	26
2.7.	Ticketing System.....	27
3.	Summary and future steps	28
	References	29
	List of acronyms	30

Tables of Figures & Tables

Document Figures

Figure 1 The GARR Cloud network infrastructure

16

Document Tables

No table of figures entries found.

Abstract

The NEANIAS project aims at delivering TRL8 (i.e. system complete and qualified) innovative services in the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research sectors to contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

UNDERWATER

ATMOSPHERE

SPACE

This document is deliverable D7.4 Infrastructure's integration report (interim) of the NEANIAS project. It contains an overview of the components, and operation of the infrastructure maintained by the NEANIAS project. The emphasis is on describing an overview of the integrated infrastructure used in the project, from two distinct aspects, namely the various resources and the ways/policies under which these are utilised.

1. Resources of the NEANIAS infrastructure

The NEANIAS infrastructure consists of many (groups of) resources in a few categories (see below). The resources to be introduced in this section are used primarily for the deployment of the production version of the services. The (mainly) physical resources are within four categories:

- 1) computing resources
- 2) storage resources
- 3) networking resources
- 4) security entities

The following sections will give an overview of the individual resources in each category.

1.1. Compute resources

1.1.1. GARR Cloud Platform

The GARR Cloud Platform hosts the main staging and production environments for NEANIAS core and thematic services. It provides an IaaS service based on OpenStack, an open-source software suite aimed at implementing cloud services in datacentres.

Users can create and operate virtual resources - in the form of virtual machines, volumes and object storage - in a multi-tenant environment spanning three different geographical regions. The persistence layer relies on volumes and objects backed by the Ceph system [1], which provides enhanced performance and data redundancy.

The GARR Cloud Platform is federated through the IDem/eduGAIN AAI and its physical infrastructures are connected to the facilities of the international research community through the high-performance network links of the GÉANT network.

At the time of writing the total of the resources allocated on the GARR Cloud Platform for NEANIAS amounts to 400 vCores, 2TB RAM, and 11TB of disk space, divided among 6 OpenStack projects.

The use of the GARR Cloud Platform and of the GARR Container Platform, described in the following section, are subject to the GARR Cloud Platform Terms of Service [2].

1.1.2. GARR Container Platform

The GARR Container Platform is based on Kubernetes [3], a popular open-source platform for container orchestration which automates the deployment, management and scaling of applications.

The GARR Container Platform Kubernetes cluster is deployed on bare metal servers to provide direct access to GPU resources which can be leveraged by containers. The persistence of the volumes in the cluster relies on the Ceph system.

It offers a multi-tenant environment whose authentication is managed by the GARR Cloud Platform OpenStack identity service (namely Keystone). GARR Cloud Platform users can thus authenticate also to the GARR Container Platform with a single account. Users are provided by default with a dedicated Kubernetes namespace with a quota of CPU cores, RAM and storage resources. Additional storage, RAM, CPU or GPU resources can be provided on demand.

The GARR Container Platform is used by NEANIAS services as both a production and staging infrastructure.

1.1.3. NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster

In addition to the GARR Container Platform, described in the previous section, a dedicated Kubernetes cluster has been deployed for NEANIAS, leveraging the GARR Cloud Platform (i.e. OpenStack) resources.

The NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster allows for a more flexible management and for optimized resource usage. Indeed, as the cluster relies on virtual machines instead of bare metal servers, Kubernetes worker nodes can be added and resized as needed. Also, the NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster users can be granted privileges that would not be allowed by policy on the GARR Container Platform. Last but not least, by deploying different services on the same cluster, a new layer of consolidation is added, allowing for a more efficient usage of the underlying resources.

At the time of writing, the NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster features a total of 40 cores and 152 GB RAM, and is being used for production services.

1.1.4. NKUA cluster

NKUA's team that participates in the project, maintains a cluster of servers of more than 3 TB of RAM and 350 cores followed by 100 TB of high availability storage. This cluster is located at the Data Center of the Department of Informatics & Telecommunications of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, at Panepistimiopolis, Ilisia, Athens, Greece and is being used by the team's researchers and scientists and is contributing resources to many projects in which the team is participating.

For NEANIAS project, NKUA is providing up to ~40 vCPUs, 256GB vRAM and 2 TB of storage, from the above cluster, with 1Gbps internal network connections. The infrastructure is based on both XEN hypervisor and Microsoft Hypervisor. The VMs are provisioned by the team's administrators, after examining requests and intended usage. If needed, NKUA will accommodate additional requests from GRNET's cloud service "OKEANOS", that is an Infrastructure as a Service service (IaaS Service).

NKUA's cluster is being used from hosting services of production, testing and development infrastructure of NEANIAS and for creating backups of those services.

1.1.5. ATHENA IT infrastructure

ATHENA IT Infrastructure provides the necessary resources and services to support the organizational needs of the Institute and the development and support of quality IT services and solutions. It consists of the hardware (HW), software (SW) and network components that are used in order to achieve the above goal. In an effort to combine the best services ATHENA Infrastructure is built upon both cloud computing and on local physical server machines.

ATHENA is having at NEANIAS's disposal the following SW and HW infrastructure. Local IT Infrastructure consists of servers hosted in ATHENA owned facilities in a dedicated server room and is largely based on Virtualization technologies in order to achieve server

consolidation and maximize the hardware's efficiency. For local IT Infrastructure, ATHENA can provide up to 106 vCPUs, 512GB RAM, 20TB storage.

Along with maintaining its own private local servers, ATHENA also takes advantage of the benefits of cloud infrastructures. The resources made available to the Greek academic and research community through GRNET's cloud service "OKEANOS" (Infrastructure as a Service service / IaaS Service), are heavily used by the Institute's users for research and development purposes. Also, in collaboration with Microsoft, its Academic program Office 365 is used for providing mail and collaboration services. Through the described infrastructures ATHENA provides to NEANIAS members and affiliates a variety of services, such as:

- Mail Services
- Directory Services used for centralized authentication and authorization
- Source Control
- Shared storage
- Virtual Private Network
- Web publishing
- Project Management and Collaboration
- Communication Services

The above services are provided and implemented using both commercial and open-source operating systems and software, such as but not limited to:

- Operating Systems: Debian Linux, Ubuntu Linux, CentOS Linux. Microsoft Windows Server
- Virtualization Software: KVM
- Database Server: PostgreSQL, MySQL, MariaDB
- Distributed Processing: Apache Hadoop

ATHENA network infrastructure provides high speed connectivity to its users and the provided services. ATHENA network connects to the Internet using a 1 Gbps fiber optics connection to GRNET. It consists of several Gigabit switches that offer wired connectivity and takes advantage of the Research Center's Wireless Infrastructure to provide high speed and reliable Wireless Connectivity. Also, through the Research Center's participation to the Eduroam Initiative, ATHENA members can use their account to gain wireless internet access in research and academic institutions in more than 70 territories in the world.

All above resources are available to support showcasing and operation for the project duration, as well as for pre-production and staging needs.

1.1.6. CITE infrastructure

CITE's infrastructure is located in two locations: (a) Kessariani, Attiki Greece and (b) Sparta, Laconia, Greece, where the main Data Center is located (on premises).

That infrastructure is used for CITE's day-to-day operation, for providing services to third parties (including Microsoft Services through Microsoft Services Provider License Agreement) and mainly for supporting CITE's R&D.

The infrastructure is mainly based on Microsoft Hypervisor and is hosting both Microsoft Windows VMs and Linux VMs.

CITE is having at NEANIAS's disposal up to 40 vCPUs, 512GB RAM, 20TB storage and allocate 50 MBps total network, offered from CITE's on premises computer room in Sparta's branch office. Those resources are available to support showcasing and operation for the project duration, as well as for pre-production and staging needs.

1.1.7. MEE0 Data Center

The MEE0 Data Center facility is an infrastructure created to support the high computing demands of MEE0 geospatial web platforms to manage geospatial data and services. Initially designed for Earth Observation data services, it has been extended to provide computational resources and hosting to a wide range of geospatial datasets. The facility gives academic, government and commercial users access to internally hosted climate and EO Data alongside a wide range of associated Services for data processing, visualization and analysis.

The fundamental characteristics of this data center facility are:

- High performance computing facilities collocated with private storage areas and large volume community satellite data sets;
- A scalable model for developing commercial and academic services and applications;
- Virtual environment for supporting any kind of virtualization needs;
- A key focus on the development and use of data integrity tools to clearly articulate the accuracy and provenance of (meta-)data, enabling users to be able to rely on the data/information;

The MEE0 Data Center is co-located in two sites, at the University of Ferrara and at the Ferrara Datacenter, interconnected to the 1 Gbps high-speed backbone GARR network. OpenNebula and OpenStack are used to manage the MEE0 Data Center virtualization resources, currently crossing +1 PByte of online storage, 3.5 PB off-line storage, +1000 cores, +4.5 TB of RAM.

1.1.8. HPC4AI infrastructure

HPC4AI (<https://hpc4ai.unito.it/>) is the Turin's High-Performance Centre for Artificial Intelligence. The first goal of HPC4AI is to establish a large and modern laboratory to co-design with industries and Small and medium-sized enterprises research and technology transfer projects. The research infrastructure aims at designing, developing and operating experimental, innovative applications and services at the convergence between High-Performance Computing and Artificial Intelligence.

Within NEANIAS, HPC4AI resources are employed for development purposes of the Space Services including Deep Learning algorithms (i.e. mainly S3-SPACE ML Service) that requires powerful GPUs for the training of the convolutional neural networks (see <https://hpc4ai.unito.it/neanias-space-services-for-structure-detection-on-large-scale-maps-with-machine-learning-in-astrophysics/2868/>).

1.1.9. ELKH Cloud

ELKH Cloud (<https://science-cloud.hu/>) is a community cloud for researchers and scientists belonging to any of the research institutes of the Eötvös Lóránd Research Network (ELKH). The infrastructure is consisting of two datacenters. One datacenter, operated by the Institute for Computer Science and Control (SZTAKI), is located near the centre of the city, in the vicinity

of the Hungarian Internet Exchange Point (BIX). The second datacenter, operated by the Wigner Research Centre for Physics, is located at a secure facility on Budapest hillside. A joint undertaking of the two datacenters, focusing on supporting the Hungarian research community, is sponsored by ELKH that plans to support a significant further development of the infrastructure increasing the overall capacity 4 times bigger than the current capacity. The datacenters work as an alliance and are facilitating similar infrastructures including several shared integration components, but have a distinct budget, as well as separate design and operation teams.

The joint IaaS/PaaS service, currently known as “ELKH Cloud”, has gained serious momentum amongst researchers, counting more than 110 projects approved by the project committee in the last three years. The effort is also catalyzed by a series of in-depth workshops, specialized service patterns supporting various scientific scenarios, a shared web portal and common authentication framework. Unique value of the service lies in close cooperation of scientific and technical personnel in a wide range of projects, resulting in a continuously evolving knowledge base for researchers and IT professionals alike.

Both datacenters are based on commodity hardware, operating on the OpenStack IaaS platform with CEPH based storage. Current capacity is 1368 vCPUs, 3.25 TB RAM, 527 TB HDD storage in a 10 Gbps networking environment. Public procurement tenders are being initiated in 2020 with an approximate budget of 3.000.000 EUR, these will substantially improve the service, resulting in overall capacity of ~3500 vCPUs, ~12 TB RAM, ~150 TB SSD storage and ~1400 TB HDD storage in a 100 Gbps internal and external networking environment. With current research focus of AI specific applications, development goals also include 2048 GPGPU cores with a total tensor capacity of ~7 PFLOPS. Resulting total capacity will be distributed between the two datacenters in an even manner.

New capacities mentioned above are planned to be available for researchers by the mid of 2021. Since ELKH Cloud is a community cloud, it is planned to be used by SZTAKI researchers for testing and development purposes.

1.2. Storage resources and repositories

1.2.1. GARR Cloud Storage

The GARR Cloud Platform provides storage in the form of both volumes and object storage. When a virtual machine is created in the GARR Cloud Platform, volume storage is provided by the OpenStack Cinder service. Cinder provides virtual block devices which can be used as hard drives by the virtual machines’ operating system.

The GARR Cloud Platform Object Storage Service is provided through the OpenStack platform and offers a RESTful interface to store, retrieve and manage objects and containers (i.e. file and directory abstractions) and their metadata (a key=value format is supported).

Both volumes and object storage are based on Ceph, which provides transparent hardware failover and efficient, transparent and redundant storage. At the time of writing, volume storage bytes are replicated 3 times, while object storage bytes are replicated 2 times. For object storage, Ceph provides a dedicated facility, i.e. the Rados Gateway, which is integrated in the GARR Cloud Platform’s OpenStack.

For what concerns Kubernetes, both the GARR Container Platform and the NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster rely on the GARR Cloud Platform storage facilities. In other words, Kubernetes PersistentVolumes are backed by the OpenStack Cinder service.

1.2.2. NEANIAS GitLab repository

GitLab [4] is an open-source web-based platform which allows software developers to manage Git source code repositories providing them with storage, issue tracking, a wiki and CI/CD pipeline facilities.

GitLab can also support the publication of artifacts through Docker registries. This allows for an integrated environment for source code management, automated building, automated testing and publishing.

A GitLab instance is available to NEANIAS developers since the early stages of the project, accessible through the NEANIAS AAI. At the time of writing, 73 users have created 89 Git repositories while the Docker registry is being used by 10 services.

1.2.3. Readthedocs repository

A key aspect to enable the integration activities at the infrastructure and at the service level is providing adequate and targeted documentation. This need has been identified from the initial panning stage of the NEANIAS activities and the tooling and processes that would facilitate it has been provisioned from the initial phases of the project.

To facilitate ease of discovery and consistent approach in the provided documentation, a single entry-point for all documentation is provided. NEANIAS provides a root level project at the popular and widely used Read the Docs online document sharing environment (<https://readthedocs.org/>). The online documentation made available under the readthedocs.org domain is also accessible through <https://docs.neanias.eu> so that readers can easily identify the scope of documentation.

This integration chosen with the Read the Docs platform aims at reusing a set of tools and accessibility facilities offered. It is not meant to host the primary source of the documentation, nor is it demanding service providers to migrate or fully manage their service documentation through it. Its main role is to host documentation artefacts that are generated through the documentation pipelines offered through NEANIAS hosted and managed resources.

The source of documentation is primarily hosted in the NEANIAS offered Source Control Management system (<https://gitlab.neanias.eu>) where service providers document their services and provide target user audience information on using and integrating with their services. In accordance to the plan set through past deliverables D7.1 [5] and D7.2 [6], provisions have been made so that:

- Service providers can reuse and link existing documentation;
- A consistent structure in presenting and navigating through the documentation is offered to end users;
- Versioning of the documentation to follow the service lifecycle is available;
- Automation pipelines have been setup to ensure that the most up to date documentation is always available.

1.2.4. NEANIAS Space repositories at IA2

IA2 (Italian center for Astronomical Archive) is an Italian Astrophysical research infrastructure that aims at co-ordinating different national initiatives to improve the quality of astrophysical data services. It aims at co-ordinating these developments and facilitating access to this data for research purposes. The IA2 is supported by INAF since 2005. IA2's main goals consist in data archiving systems and safety, including data hosting and data curation and preservation, data and metadata distribution over geographical sites, access services including publication under the standards of the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA).

NEANIAS Space services access IA2 repositories for the Space Service S1 ViaLactea, holding the data sources by means of the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB). The VLKB contents is about 2 TB, including datasets and catalogues from different instruments and missions. In particular, those include spectral radio cubes from surveys and (a few) pointed observations:

- CHaMP: <http://www.astro.ufl.edu/~peterb/research/champ/rbank/>
- HOPS: http://awalsh.ivec.org/hops/public/data_cubes.php
- ThrUMMS: <http://www.astro.ufl.edu/~peterb/research/thrumms/rbank/>
- JCMT-HARPS: <http://www.cadc-ccda.hia-ihp.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/en/jcmt/>
- MALT90: <http://atoa.atnf.csiro.au/MALT90>

As well as infrared and radio continuum maps from the following surveys:

- CORNISH: <http://cornish.leeds.ac.uk/public/index.php>
- MAGPIS: <http://third.ucllnl.org/gps/>
- VGPS: <http://www.ras.ucalgary.ca/VGPS/>
- SGPS: <http://www.atnf.csiro.au/research/HI/sgps/queryForm.html>
- CGPS: <http://www.ras.ucalgary.ca/CGPS/products/>
- VLASS: <https://archive-new.nrao.edu/vlass/quicklook/>
- Hi-GAL: <https://tools.ssdc.asi.it/HiGAL.jsp>
- MIPS GAL: <http://irsa.ipac.caltech.edu/data/SPITZER/MIPSGAL/>
- WISE: <http://irsa.ipac.caltech.edu/Missions/wise.html>
- GLIMPSE:
<https://irsa.ipac.caltech.edu/data/SPITZER/docs/spitzermission/observingprograms/legacy/glimpse/>

These data resources were taken from the aforementioned data collections and stored at IA2 to fix some metadata annotations to let the added value of the services work with homogeneous settings. For this reason, the links provided above might not provide exactly the same files/datasets as the one available through the ViaLactea service. A similar caveat applies to some catalogues, like the WISE one, that, being too big, were filtered to fit the galactic plane as defined by the Hi-GAL survey (the starting point of the VIALACTEA project). Also, a few collections are not made available to non-authorized users since they have a different privacy policy (NEANIAS user authentication and authorization is in place to control access to them).

1.2.5. MEE0 storage and repositories

MEE0 has implemented an ICT infrastructure based on a distributed architecture. The proprietary internal resource is the MEE0 Data Facility (MEE0-DAF) which is a high-

performance infrastructure with a storage capability of about 5 PB (1.2PB on-line) created to support the high computing demand of geospatial data and services. The external resources are the cloud computing infrastructures which are already hosting MEE0 services. In its last configuration, MEE0-DAF presents a distributed architecture made of two DPIs (Data processing Infrastructures) exposing a unique cloud infrastructure operated by means of Open Nebula and OpenStack cloud solutions.

MEE0 provides access to EO data stored in external storage resources, namely the Copernicus DIAS infrastructures and the Registry of Open Data on AWS. To optimize the exploitation of Sentinel-3 and Sentinel-5P datasets, the access to Cloud Optimized Geotiff (COG) products through the NEANIAS Data Access System (DAS) is enabled.

1.3. Networking

1.3.1. Architecture, capabilities, functionalities of the GARR network

The GARR network (Figure 1) is an e-infrastructure boasting about 15 thousand km of optical fibres in Italy. It reaches 4.5 million users approximately and interconnects over 1000 sites between research organisations, universities, research hospitals, cultural institutions, libraries, museums and schools.

In order to allow researchers to collaborate with their peers regardless from their location, the GARR network interconnects to the other research and education networks worldwide and to the global internet. Since its beginnings, GARR has been part of the pan-European network GÉANT, and it is one of its shareholders together with the other National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) in Europe.

The GARR Cloud infrastructure spans five sites in southern Italy. The three main sites are interconnected through 100 Gbps links to form a ring, while the two secondary sites are interconnected through 40 Gbps links to two of the main sites, forming two secondary rings.

Figure 1 The GARR Cloud network infrastructure

1.4. Security entities and mechanisms

1.4.1. PKI, Certificates

For protecting confidentiality, integrity and authenticity, SSL certificates are being used for encrypted connections and/or authentication between NEANIAS's services. These services are often having their FQDN on local domain and for this reason it was needed to implement a NEANIAS Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) - internal Certificate Authority (CA).

To implement NEANIAS PKI, a NEANIAS ROOT CA and a NEANIAS CA (intermediate) were created. The ROOT CA certificate is self-signed while intermediate one is signed by the ROOT CA. Their private keys are stored securely and separated from their public keys.

When a NEANIAS's service needs to contact another NEANIAS's service or if it needs to authenticate to another NEANIAS's service using a certificate, then the service owner is creating a private key for the specific service and a certificate signing request for that key. This certificate signing request is given to NEANIAS's PKI administrators for signing it with NEANIAS CA (intermediate) so that they return to the service owner the signed request (certificate).

If a key is compromised/missed/removed, the service owner of that key is requesting, from the PKI administrators, to revoke that key. The NEANIAS's PKI is keeping a database with all signed requests, revoked keys and created revocation lists for both NEANIAS Root CA (containing revoked intermediate CA's certificates) and for NEANIAS CA (having all revoked certificates signed by that CA).

Those revocation lists are published, over http for compatibility reasons, at the following urls:

- http://ca.neanias.eu/crl/neanias_root_ca.crl
- http://ca.neanias.eu/crl/neanias_ca.crl

Some of the scenarios that NEANIAS PKI is used (authentication or/and encryption) are as follows:

- Sending log data from services to logging service;
- Elastic cluster, nodes connection;
- Sending accounting data from services to accounting service;
- Services' connections to configuration service;
- Services' connections to service instance registry service;
- Zookeeper cluster nodes' connections.

1.4.2. GARR Cloud Authentication Mechanisms

The GARR Cloud Platform supports several authentication mechanisms. The preferred authentication is through eduGAIN, the research community identity federation, based on the SAML protocol. As a fallback, users can authenticate through Google's OpenID Connect facilities or, finally, can use a local username and password pair.

As briefly reported in Section 1.1.2, the GARR Container Platform and the GARR Cloud Platform share the same accounts. This is made possible by an integration of Kubernetes with Keystone, the OpenStack identity service. For details, please refer to [7].

From the user perspective, he/she should register to the GARR Cloud Platform. Once the request has been approved, he/she will be able to log into the OpenStack dashboard. From there he/she can create with a few clicks a set of application credentials and download a Kubernetes configuration file, which is ready to be used to authenticate the Kubernetes client to the GARR Container Platform.

1.4.3. Gitlab Token

Most of the operations provided by Gitlab can be used through the API which is protected by personal access tokens. A token can be generated for any tool that needs access to GitLab API (https://docs.gitlab.com/ee/user/profile/personal_access_tokens.html).

This token can be used for:

- **Read user:** Allows access to the read-only endpoints under /users. Essentially, any of the GET requests in the Users API are allowed.
- **API:** Grants complete read/write access to the API, including all groups and projects, the container registry, and the package registry.
- **Read API:** Grants read access to the API, including all groups and projects, the container registry, and the package registry.
- **Read registry:** Allows to read (pull) container registry images if a project is private and authorization is required.
- **Write registry:** Allows to write (push) container registry images if a project is private and authorization is required.
- **Read repository: Allows read-only access (pull) to the repository through git clone.**
- **Write repository:** Allows read-write access (pull, push) to the repository through git clone. Required for accessing Git repositories over HTTP when 2FA is enabled.
- **Use GitLab API:** Allows read-write access (pull, push) to the repository through git clone. Required for accessing Git repositories over HTTP when 2FA is enabled

The token can be created as a personal access tokens in GitLab through the account profile or programmatically through a Rails console session. Revocation of the token may also happen two ways such as through the GitLab profile or programmatically.

The token is associated to the user who created it, so the token has similar rights as the user has. For instance, if the user is not a member of a project, the token cannot read docker registry of that project.

The Gitlab API allows to use the password of the user for doing tasks with GitLab (i.e., to pull image from the docker repository) but this is very dangerous because the password will be stored on the machine. The personal access token is much safer because contains only a subset of user rights and can be revoked quickly.

1.4.4. AAI

NEANIAS offers a horizontal AAI solution that is utilized by all the underlying NEANIAS services. This solution focuses on both Authentication and Authorization aspects.

With respect to authentication, the identity federation paradigm [8] is used to facilitate the authentication and registration to the NEANIAS catalog of users, principals that are

Infrastructures integration report (interim)

authenticated through external identity providers. This approach enables the NEANIAS AAI to be able to integrate and federate its user base with a large number of available identity providers. This capability is based on the usage of widely accepted standards such as Open ID Connect [9] in a manner ensuring untampered identity and profile information propagation from trusted identity providers.

With respect to authorization, the following alternatives are made available and can be utilized based on specific service needs. It should be noted that these alternatives are not necessarily mutually exclusive, and a combination can be used by some service as seems most fitting.

- Role based – The mechanisms to define roles within the NEANIAS AAI Single Sign On (SSO) solution is provided. These roles can be subsequently assigned to authenticated users and the information flow down to services with each request as the respective caller claims. The roles can be defined with a global application scope, or they can be client specific. This way, each service can define a set of roles that do not clash in semantics with other service needs. In addition to roles, user groups are employed and semantics on group membership can be utilized by the services directly, or indirectly to effectively administer role assignments to groups of users
- Resource based – A mechanism to define ad hoc resources within the NEANIAS AAI service has been investigated. The purpose of such a construct would allow NEANIAS services, through respective exposed API endpoints to autonomously define resources and manage user authorization over them. The scope of these resources can be determined in an ad hoc fashion by each service. This approach is available to service providers that wish to tightly integrate with the NEANIAS AAI API beyond the offered OIDC protocol
- Service Specific – Each service has diverse authorization requirements. For this reason, in addition to the Role and Resource based authorization that are offered horizontally, each service can employ fine grained authorization policies within its own business logic. For this case, the horizontal NEANIAS solution provides consistent client subject identifiers and any origin information it has available to facilitate in-service solutions, possibly, ranging from access control lists (ACL) to custom business rules

The authentication flow that passes through the centrally managed NEANIAS AAI service exposes suitable user info endpoints [10] through which the respective id tokens can be used to retrieve the caller's claims. This information is provided in the form of a JWT token [11] containing information to be utilized by servicing components.

To support the full lifetime of a service, three realms are available to cover authentication and authorization needs for:

- Development
- Staging
- Production

At each one of these realms, different external identity providers can be supported depending on needs. Additionally, different users and role assignments can facilitate the requirements of the different environment use cases.

1.4.5. Reverse proxy

All NEANIAS services are exposed to end-users using the HTTPS scheme, with SSL certificates obtained by the Let's Encrypt Certification Authority. To achieve this, we use the Kubernetes Nginx Ingress controller [12] at our production-grade Kubernetes cluster that is implemented over OpenStack Virtual Machines. We chose this approach as most of our services are either already deployed in this cluster or are currently moving there. In any case, this ingress controller can also proxy against external services, i.e., ones not deployed in the same Kubernetes cluster.

The Nginx ingress controller comprises 3 replicas with distinct IP addresses. Additionally, we also deployed cert-manager [13], which is the component tasked to obtain and renew TLS certificates from Let's Encrypt. We use domain-name-based routing for our reverse proxy, where each service has its own DNS name and the reverse proxy routes based on the hostname field of the HTTP request.

A service deployed in the same cluster needs a simple ingress configuration manifest where its domain name and the Kubernetes service name are declared. Using this, the reverse proxy routes, using a round-robin approach, incoming requests to different replicas of the service.

For services deployed outside the cluster, we define an "Endpoint" for its IP address and port combination, and we configure the reverse proxy to route to this endpoint. Since this is a single endpoint, an "external" service with multiple replicas employs an OpenStack-provided Load Balancer as its endpoint. In turn, the Load Balancer distributes the load to all the service's replicas.

In any case, services point their DNS name records to all three IPs of the Nginx ingress controller, so that round-robin DNS can assist in randomly utilizing all nodes of the reverse proxy.

2. Integration policies in the NEANIAS infrastructure

The NEANIAS resources (described in Section 1) are utilised by the service developers, owners and providers. This section intends to summarise how the NEANIAS infrastructure is utilised focusing on the processes applied. Policies and best practices are applied for a few categories like documentation, code release, integration, packaging, testing, deployment and ticketing. In the following sections, these categories will be detailed.

2.1. Documentation Rendering

As reported in Section 1.2.3, the main documentation for the NEANIAS project is hosted and served by Readthedocs, while its source is stored in the NEANIAS GitLab.

The documentation is updated through an integrated CI/CD pipeline: when the documentation source in a git repository on Gitlab is updated, a webhook is ran, which triggers Readthedocs to retrieve a fresh copy of the documentation sources and render them in HTML. For more information, please refer to [4].

2.2. Code Release

The code of most of the NEANIAS services is stored on the NEANIAS Gitlab (see also Section 1.2.2). A new software release typically results in the creation of a new artifact and its publication, as described in [4]. Several NEANIAS services employ Gitlab's CI/CD facilities to automate this process: at every commit a Docker image is automatically built, a container is spun up, tests are executed against it, and if these are successful, the image is published to the Gitlab Docker registry.

2.3. Integration

The solutions described in the following sections will detail, how the NEANIAS project organises the shareable core services to be utilised by the Thematic services which is the primary goal of the project. The integration will provide a benefit for the individual services in terms of centralisation, reusability, interoperability, manageability, etc. The aim of the core services is to cover and implement common features in one service – some of these are the following: authentication for identifying users, logging to track the operation of the services, accounting for tracking the utilisation of the services, data sharing to let users manage their data more easily, cataloguing to organise the services in a structured way.

2.3.1. Authentication

On the technical level, integration with the NEANIAS AAI Service takes place using the OIDC [9] protocol and the supported grant flows that are enabled per client. The identified grant flows that have been enabled for the client include:

- Authorization Code Grant Flow – Commonly used flow for browser-based applications that support user facing authentication flows
- Client Credentials Grant Flow – Service to service invocation authorization

- Implicit Grant Flow – Less commonly used flow for trusted clients without the need for backchannel communication

These grant flows are not mutually exclusive. For each service client, multiple grant flows can be enabled. For example, typically, a service may utilize the Authorization Grant Flow to authenticate its users and the Client Credentials Grant Flow to retrieve access tokens to utilize when invoking other services.

On the process level, in order for a client service to be registered with the NEANIAS AAI service and be trusted to be included in the authorization flows provided by the service, as well as to update the available configuration for the service, a well-defined process needs to be used. This process is defined and governed through the Service Management System that NEANIAS employs through the relevant tooling offered for the purpose.

As an example, for the processes employed, the following high-level description drafts the process of registering a new service client:

- Submit a support request ticket describing the need
- Provide information on the service, consents required, service name, description, logos, etc.
- Provide links for Terms of Use, Privacy Notice, contact person information, and other needed documentation and information
- Define the scope of registration (development, staging, production)
- Define the roles and groups that the service will require its users to be assigned with to access service functionality
 - Individual user access requests are handled through separate processes
- The registration takes place and the connection information is securely transmitted back to the requestor

2.3.2. Logging

The Logging Service provides an aggregation functionality through which NEANIAS services can accumulate logs that are generated in a distributed fashion in a single centralized repository through well-defined endpoints and library utilities facilitating the transformation, enrichment and indexing of the log entries.

At a technical level, the NEANIAS Logging Service is backed by an ELK stack. The ELK stack consists of an Elasticsearch [14] index backend that stores data and makes them searchable, Logstash [15] that facilitates the transformation of log entries extraction of additional metadata and homogenization of logged entries, Kibana [16] that offers visualization, aggregation and filtering graphical user interface over the indexed entries.

To facilitate the aggregation of log and lower the integration barrier for individual services, a non-intrusive approach is promoted using the Beats [17] framework for data shipping. Specifically, beats modules for both file as well as http transfer are provided with supportive configuration. Given the wide adoption and general availability of multiple integration utilities and endpoints for the selected stack, service providers can utilize any of the available and widely adopted integration methodologies.

To homogenize but not restrict integrating services to a single strict model, log templates for log entry formats are provided along with the respective Logstash transformation templates

that extracts a limited common set of information. This way, a homogenized set of information is made available for log browsing and aggregation operations. All formats support extension points which can be used to contain additional, service specific information. From the security aspect, information provided by individual service providers are linked to Logging Service data structures directly through the identification mechanisms employed for the communication. This ensures that each log producer has a dedicated, isolated storage for their logs.

Access to the produced logs is limited through centrally managed authorization using the NEANIAS AAI role assignment capabilities. Individual users can be granted access to specific service logs.

On the process level, through the NEANIAS Service Management System, processes are defined, among others, so that:

- A service provider can request access to the logging service and be accepted as a log producer
- Be granted access to browse the logs generated by their service
- Delegate access to the logs
- Refine retention policies for the service logs

2.3.3. Accounting

The NEANIAS Accounting service provides an aggregation functionality through which NEANIAS services can centrally log accounting information as it is gradually accumulated by their usage from the respective authorized clients.

At a technical level, the NEANIAS Accounting Service is backed by an ELK stack. To facilitate reuse at the technical and the resource level, as well as to lower the integration barrier for NEANIAS services, the ELK resources utilized by the Logging Service 2.3.2 are shared for their aggregation mechanisms and reused also by the Accounting Service.

To homogenize but not restrict integrating services to a single strict model, the accounting service aggregation process requires identification of accountable information at the producing service end. This can take place by explicit accounting information production, log parsing, or any other means that service providers choose to employ. To facilitate ease of adoption and integration, accounting log entry identification expressions and transformations are provided.

The accounting model supported is based around an open definition principal. Information categories are defined, but individual services are free to define accountable resources and actions based on their business needs.

From the security aspect, information provided by individual service providers are linked to accounting service data structures directly through the identification mechanisms employed for the communication. This ensures that each accounting model producer has a dedicated, isolated storage for their entries.

Access to the produced entries is limited through centrally managed authorization using the NEANIAS AAI role assignment capabilities as well as internal Accounting Service Access Control Lists (ACL). Individual users can be granted access to specific service accounting information.

In addition to service-based accounting information, authenticated users that have been centrally granted access to the Accounting Service can access accounting information that has been collected for their usage of the services.

On the process level, through the NEANIAS Service Management System, processes are defined, among others, so that:

- A service provider can request access to the accounting service and be accepted as a log producer
- Be granted access to browse the accounting information generated by their service
- Delegate access to the accounting information
- Request access to retrieve personal usage accounting information

2.3.4. Data Sharing Service

We employ Nextcloud [18][18], deployed at the GARR infrastructure, relying on its storage resources (Section 1.2.1) and accessible via <https://files.neanias.eu>, as a means to achieve the following:

1. Share data between each service's components
2. Store long-term data, such as service demonstration files
3. Allow the users to upload data and use them via NEANIAS services
4. Allow users to access result files produced by the NEANIAS services

To elaborate, a service that has many components (e.g., a web server and a computation service), uses Nextcloud to send input data from the web server to the computation service, and also send output files from the computation service back to the web component for the latter to be able to output them as HTML pages.

Users are also able to upload their files on Nextcloud, and either "share" these files with a NEANIAS service so that they can be used as input, or directly "mount" their personal space at Nextcloud and use it directly, as is the case for JupyterHub-based NEANIAS services.

Finally, users are free to form communities and exchange files via Nextcloud between them, towards achieving common goals. Users are also free to download results produced by NEANIAS services that are accessible from their personal workspace.

Please, note that the Nextcloud deployment at NEANIAS is not a generic file sharing or data storage service. It is only intended as a means for users to exchange files with the NEANIAS services for the short-term. For example, NEANIAS services frequently clean-up files submitted by users or outputs from past executions, to conserve space. For longer-term storage, end-users are encouraged to use public repositories, such as Zenodo [19], or their institution provided file hosting services.

2.3.5. Service Catalogue

NEANIAS catalogue offers to users a single-entry point to all NEANIAS list of services, including core, thematic services as well as datasets and other resources. The catalogue portal offers functionalities for users to browse the available services, search and filter along EOSC compliant classification, such as scientific domain or category of a service, the maturity of the service, the intended use, etc., as well as to compare NEANIAS service offerings. The service catalogue enables NEANIAS service providers to manage their service portfolio in NEANIAS

and model their services based on the EOSC guidelines. In brief it offers the following functionality towards

- NEANIAS service providers: They can manage their services (add, update, make public\nonpublic in the catalogue, etc) , model them based on EOSC guidelines, view statistics about user visits related to their service offerings and finally register and synchronize their services with the EOSC portal, via API communication.
- NEANIAS end users (researchers and other stakeholders): They can view the public list of services developed in NEANIAS, search and discover all thematic and core services, browse on the details of each service, compare services and personalize their experience by rating services or adding services in a favorite list.

Service catalogue is a Web application built in JAVAEE (<https://www.oracle.com/java/technologies/java-ee-glance.html>) and PostgreSQL offering a list of REST methods for managing a catalogue of EOSC compliant services. It integrates with the NEANIAS AAI for user authentication.

2.4. Packaging

Most of the deployment of NEANIAS project is based on Docker images, this because the production platform is Kubernetes, a container orchestrator.

Docker images need to be available in the GitLab container registry, to do this, the developer needs to build the image by marking it with the GitLab registry prefix and then push it

These steps can be automated with a GitLab pipeline that updates the docker image version. The pipeline must be formed with following step:

- Docker build: this phase clones the GitLab project and runs Docker build
- Docker push: this phase is executed only if the previous phase is completed without error, in this case run Docker push command to load image on GitLab container registry.

In this way all images are available on GitLab, that provides image without limit or restriction.

2.5. Testing

There are several ways to test an application, this paragraph describes how to test a RESTful http application with Postman (<https://www.postman.com/use-cases/api-testing/>). The choice of software falls on Postman for the following reasons:

- Provide different client interfaces: desktop, CLI, API
- Make it possible to share a test collection with team and partner
- Manage your end-to-end lifecycle, from design to deployment
- Provide a platform runtime service to manage your API collections
- Provide free and enterprise edition
- It's easy to integrate with a CI tool (Jenkins <https://www.jenkins.io/> or Gitlab)

As described in Section 1.2.2 on GitLab, it's possible to use GitLab CI to automatize deployment and testing, in this case is recommended to use Postman. The software automates manual tests and integrates them into your CI/CD pipeline to ensure any code changes won't break the API in production.

With postman is possible to define a collection (<https://learning.postman.com/docs/running-collections/intro-to-collection-runs/>) of tests that can run in local or remote environment. This collection can be run on a GitLab CI with the support of Newman. Newman (<https://learning.postman.com/docs/running-collections/using-newman-cli/command-line-integration-with-newman/>) is a command line collection runner easy to integrate with Docker (<https://learning.postman.com/docs/running-collections/using-newman-cli/newman-with-docker/>). Obviously, the service must be up and running, so a staging deployment phase on the GitLab CI is required previous to the test phase.

2.6. Deployment

The NEANIAS service infrastructure consists of numerous thematic and core services. In the NEANIAS project most (but not all) of the production services are deployed on one of the following resources:

- GARR OpenStack Cloud Platform (see Section 1.1.1). This cloud provides the resources used primarily for hosting the services.
- GARR Container Platform (see Section 1.1.2) realised by Kubernetes on bare metal resources.
- NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster (see Section 1.1.3) is also realised by Kubernetes, but on top of the GARR OpenStack Cloud Platform

The deployment process is based on the category of the resource and the requirements of the service. There are several different deployment methods applied for the services by the developers and providers. Here the overview of the most popular deployment methods is listed.

For those services where the deployment is performed on virtual machine(s), the most popular way of handling (launching/shutdown) the virtual machines are the manual way through the OpenStack dashboard. At the moment there are service deployed on multi-VM resources where orchestration would be needed. For example, the catalogue service is deployed on a single VM, while the Horovod [20] cluster is deployed on manually launched virtual machines. On these virtual machines, the most well-known and popular tools (for deployment) are used i.e., apt package manager for Ubuntu and yum for CentOS. Ansible configuration manager is not yet utilised, but is planned to be used in the future. Ansible is powerful for complicated, distributed deployment where software components have to be installed on multiple Virtual Machines. A good example for this is the Horovod cluster.

Most of the services are realised by containers and docker images. The typical deployment tools applied in the project for setting up the services are Docker compose and Docker run tools. For example, U2 service applies the first, while the second one applied by Horovod cluster.

Stepping towards a more intelligent way of service deployment and execution framework, the Kubernetes cluster is the most popular environment for hosting services. There are two

Kubernetes cluster provided for the NEANIAS service providers as it has been mentioned at the beginning of this section. In both cases the primary tool for deployment is Helm[21], while in rare situations (when the original helm recipe does not fit to our need) basic Kubernetes manifest is also used.

Finally, we can mention a special deployment method accessible at the level of users. This deployment method is realised by the JupyterHub services. In case of JupyterHub, the Jupyter Notebook server is launched and deployed on the Kubernetes cluster initiated by the user of JupyterHub. This worth mentioning, the details of the deployment is described by the JupyterHub configuration.

2.7. Ticketing System

For the needed communication between NEANIAS service providers, organization of activities and interoperation related activities, NEANIAS offers, in addition to other communication channels, a single ticketing system through which technical partners can coordinate their activities. The scope of this ticket system is to cover:

- Interoperation protocols
- API harmonization
- Deployment and runtime issues
- Issue and Service request tracking within the project
- Other integration and development activities

The target users of this ticketing system are the NEANIAS consortium members, service providers and service maintainers and the tracked issues involve primarily the interoperation of the NEANIAS services.

The ticketing system is based on a Redmine software instance and is available through <https://ticketing.neanias.eu/projects/neanias-software/>

For issues involving the underlying physical or virtual infrastructures, the specific provider's ticketing systems are employed. This allows to involve key persons, which may not be directly involved in NEANIAS, in the issue resolution.

3. Summary and future steps

This document gives an overview of the infrastructure resources and the way how these resources are used in the NEANIAS project. The document also focuses on the integration related solutions and best practices.

Regarding the infrastructure resources, the primary resource provider in the project is GARR with its cloud and container platforms, storage and networking resources hosting most (almost all) of the NEANIAS services while other infrastructures are used for development purposes.

The provided resources are used to support the different phases of development and operation of the services as well as to support several core/basic services providing common functionalities for the other ones.

The infrastructure integration, operations and management are currently being further improved by introducing service management system. The NEANIAS SMS system will rely on FitSM standards and will support the management of users, complaints, releases of the services, etc. The SMS system is currently under development and will be reported in subsequent deliverables.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication, Authorisation, Identification
ACL	Access Control List
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Certificate Authority
CEPH	Name of an open-source software storage platform
CLI	Command Line Interface
eduGAIN	an international interederation service interconnecting research and education identity federations
ELK	Elasticsearch Logstash and Kibana
ELKH	Eotvos Lorand Kutato Halozat
FitSM	Family of standards for lightweight IT service management
FLOPS	Floating-point Operations Per Seconds
FQDN	Fully Qualified Domain Name
GEANT	pan-European data network for the research and education community
GPGPU	General-purpose computing on graphics processing units
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IVOA	International Virtual Observatory Alliance
MEEO	Meteorological and Environmental Earth Observation
OIDC	OAuth and OpenID Connect
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
SaaS	Software as a Service
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SMS	Service Management System
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TLS	Transport Layer Security
VMs	Virtual Machines